

Synthesis of Novel 4-Styrylcoumarins from Coumarin-4-acetic Acids

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Coumarins have varied useful properties¹. An early review² on the Pechmann reaction describes the synthetic routes for coumarins. In our earlier communication 3-phenyl-4-styrylcoumarins and their conversion into 3-phenyl-acetic acid beznisoxazoles³ were reported. We report here a route for synthesis of new 4-styrylcoumarins from coumarin-4-acetic acids^{4,5} (1, 4). Coumarin-4-acetic acids were synthesised from the appropriate phenols and citric acid using sulphuric acid as condensing agent. The coumarin-4-acetic acids (1, 4) were condensed with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde and *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde in piperidine medium to obtain 4-styryl-coumarins (5–10). Bromination of 5 and 6,

instead of giving addition to ethylenic double bond, gave 3-bromo-substituted products (11, 12). Acetylation of the 7-hydroxyl group in 5 and 6 gave the corresponding 7-acetoxy derivatives (13, 14). However, coumarin-4-acetic acids substituted with a methyl group at the 6- or 7-position did not give condensation with aldehydes to form the corresponding 4 styrylcoumarins. It seems that the presence of a 7-hydroxy group is necessary for the condensation with aldehydes to give 4-styrylcoumarins. Out of a number of solvents used, only piperidine was found to be successful.

Decarboxylation of coumarin-4-acetic acids on heating above their m.ps. gave the corresponding

known 4-methylcoumarins which were prepared by known methods for direct comparison. The new and previously known coumarins prepared during this work are given in Table 1. The coumarin-4-acetic acids were screened for their anticancer and anti-AIDS activities and were found to be inactive.

TABLE 1 — PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1—14*

Compd. no.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	Yield %	M. p °C
1	CH ₂ COOH	H	OH	H	60	203 ^a
2	CH ₂ COOH	H	CH ₃	H	50	190 ^a
3	CH ₂ COOH	CH ₃	H	H	26	181 ^a
4	CH ₂ COOH	Cl	OH	H	25	207 ^a
5	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃)	H	OH	H	40	179
6	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃)	Cl	OH	H	45	279
7	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	H	OH	H	40	175
8	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	Cl	OH	H	50	275
9	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂ -p	H	OH	H	60	171
10	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂ -p	Cl	OH	H	56	281
11	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃)-p	H	OH	Br	60	194
12	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃)-p	Cl	OH	Br	65	235
13	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃)-p	H	OAc	H	70	157
14	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃)-p	Cl	OAc	H	70	258

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and Cl analyses
^a Refs. 4 and 5.

Experimental

Coumarin-4-acetic acid (1—4): Anhydrous citric acid (10 g) was heated with concentrated H₂SO₄ (30 ml) on a water-bath until the evolution of CO₂ ceased. After cooling, the appropriate phenol (4 g) was added to it followed by concentrated H₂SO₄ (10 ml). The reaction mixture was kept for 24 h at room temperature. It was then poured into ice-cold water and solid which separated was crystallised from dilute ethanol to obtain the products which were identical with authentic reference samples (m.p., m.m.p., tlc and co-tlc).

4-Styrylcoumarins (5—10): Coumarin-4-acetic acid (1 or 4; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in piperidine (20 ml) and the appropriate aldehyde (benzaldehyde or anisaldehyde or *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, 0.01 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 140° for 2 h. It was then cooled, diluted with water and acidified with dilute HCl. The solid obtained was crystallised from 98% ethanol as yellow crystals: 7-hydroxy-4-(*p*-methoxystyryl)coumarin, m.p. 179°; λ_{max} 322 nm; ν_{max}

3 540 (phenolic OH), 1 600 (benzene), 1 680 (ester, coumarin), 1 450 and 1 390 (C—H def, sym def), 990 (CH=CH) and 850 cm⁻¹ (ArH); δ (EM-360 spectrophotometer, 60 MHz; CDCl₃-DMSO-d₆, standard Me₄Si) 3.24 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.3 (2H, m, CH=CH), 6.15 (1H, s, Het-H), 6.8—7.6 (7H, m, ArH) and 10 (1H, s, OH); *m/z* 294 (M⁺, 24.4%) 292 (23.7) 276, (19.8), 266 (18.4), 207 (13.7), base peak 43.0.

Bromination of 5 and 6: The coumarin (5 or 6; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in acetic acid and a solution of bromine in acetic acid (0.01 mol) was added to it with stirring. After 10 min the mixture was poured into ice-water. The solid obtained was crystallised from 98% ethanol to obtain 11 and 12 as yellow crystalline materials: 11 ν_{max} 3 500 (OH), 1 780—1 680 (coumarin O—CO—), 1 600 (benzene), 1 450 (C—H def), 1 320, 1 260, 1 190, 1 130, 1050, 1 000, 800 and 610 cm⁻¹; δ (100 MHz; solvent DMSO-d₆, standard Me₄Si), 2.3 (2H, m, CH=CH), 3.24 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.8—7.8 (7H, m, ArH), 11 (1H, s, OH); *m/z* 373 (M⁺ 29.4%), 371 (24.9), 333 (8.59), 329 (8.59), 310 (9.50), base peak 121.

Acetylation of 5 and 6: A mixture of 5 or 6 (0.01 mol), acetic anhydride (0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.5 g) was heated on a water-bath for 40 min. The mixture was then diluted with water and the solid thus formed was crystallised from 98% ethanol to obtain 13 or 14.

Formation of 4-methylcoumarin from 1—4: Coumarin-4-acetic acids (1—4) were heated above their m.p. in an oil-bath when CO₂ was evolved and the liquid formed turned solid on cooling. The residue was crystallised from dilute ethanol to obtain the products (m.p., m.m.p., tlc and co-tlc with the authentic samples prepared).

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